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Correction: Ga and Ce ion-doped phosphate glass fibres with antibacterial properties and their composite for wound healing applications

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The authors regret that in the original article the affiliation list is presented incorrectly. The corrected list is shown above. This change does not affect the affiliation tags used in the author list, which therefore remain the same.

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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